

THERMOPLASTIC BONDING FOR STRUCTURAL APPLICATIONS: "THE ROLE OF PROCESSING"

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ABSTRACT

By varying the thermal processing of polyetherketoneetherketoneketone (PEKEKK) during bonding of tensile butt joints, tensile strengths of 138 MPa are achieved. This study investigates the effects of hold time above the melt temperature (T_m) and at the isothermal recrystallization temperature (T_{iso}). Bond strength increases with soak time above T_m and at T_{iso} . Extended soak times above T_m may cause a reduction in strength due to excessive polymer squeeze out. Additionally, the effects of cooling rate have been investigated. The thermal process cycle eliminates residual spherulitic crystallinity and enhances the growth of high strength transcrystalline regions at the metal-polymer interface.

INTRODUCTION

The bulk of research in adhesive joining has focused primarily on thermosets, specifically epoxies. However, thermoset based adhesives have two main drawbacks: most are not environmentally friendly and the joint formation generally involves a time consuming cure process. Recent developments in the use of hot-melt thermoplastic adhesives have continued growing in popularity due to several reasons. These adhesives do not involve solvents, the chemically resistive bonds can be formed very quickly, and they can support a wide variety of applications. Currently, industrial consumption in packaging and product assembly applications are more than 800 million lb. annually [1]. The polymers used commercially as hot-melt adhesives, such as polypropylene, polyesters and polyethylene, soften at temperatures on the order of 150 °C. Present applications typically require low structural properties from these adhesives. Because of the minimal demands placed on these structural adhesives the effects of the process induced morphology on the performance have not been fully investigated and utilized.

Recently, however, thermoplastic families such as polyarylktones and polysulfones have been evaluated for bonding with metals [2,3]. The high interfacial shear strengths of PEEK-steel bonds were attributed to Fe and Cr-O-C linkages. These studies involved the use of slurries and focused on the interfacial chemistry. Thin-film thermoplastics are being explored for bonding for structural orthopaedic applications [4,5]. These studies have demonstrated that the polymer-metal bond is stronger than the bulk polymer in PEK to steel joints and PEKEKK to titanium joints.

These findings are of particular importance to the orthopaedic industry. Metal implants replacing sections of bone in the body typically have a porous metal coating bonded to the surface to promote bone growth and enhance the implant/bone durability. In general,

metallurgical bonding method such as diffusion bonding are used. However, a dramatic drop in fatigue strength can occur in the base metal due to notches at the porous metal coating/metal implant bond sites [5]. However, by bonding the porous metal coating to the implant with a thermoplastic adhesive, this fatigue strength degradation can be avoided.

The goal of the present study is to establish the role of processing in thermoplastic structural adhesive joints to metals using thin-film polymers. A design of experiments was performed to determine the effects of the thermal process cycle on strength. The joint strengths are evaluated using statistical analysis. In addition, the tensile specimens are examined using x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

MATERIALS

The polymeric adhesive used in this study is PEKEKK (polyetherketonetherketoneketone) from BASF and is sold under the tradename of Ultrapek®. Ultrapek is a semi-crystalline polymer that exhibits excellent physical properties: high strength and rigidity at both room and elevated temperatures and good thermal and dimensional stability [6]. In addition, Ultrapek's unique semi-crystalline morphology (see Fig. 1) provides for good resistance to chemical attack or hydrolysis [7]. This combination of superior mechanical and highly inert chemical properties make Ultrapek an ideal polymer for use in the medical field, specifically for biomedical implants. The polymer was supplied in the form of a 0.0254 mm thick film. Titanium alloy (Ti-6Al-4V) specimens (see Fig. 2) are bonded together using Ultrapek film to create tensile butt joints.

PROCEDURE

SURFACE PREPARATION

Adhesive joint strength and long-term durability are influenced greatly by the adherend surfaces. The sensitivity to the morphology and cleanliness of the surface has been a constraining factor in the use of adhesives. In order to ensure that adhesive joints of good quality are created, a surface preparation process is used to clear the bonding surfaces of contaminants and generate a consistent surface morphology. This surface morphology allows the creation of mechanical interlocking between the adherend and the polymer.

The titanium specimens are gritblasted with 60 grit alumina after machining. The samples are measured with a Mituyo Surftest 201 to verify that all parts have a surface roughness (Ra) between 2.54 to 5.08 microns. Afterwards, the specimens are cleaned ultrasonically using a Branson Ultrasonic Cleaner (Model 5200) for 1/2 hour in water with detergent, deionized water, and finally in isopropyl alcohol. This process was found to achieve superior bonding of the titanium alloy in previous studies [4].

APPARATUS

After cleaning, a disk of adhesive film (thickness = 0.0254 mm, diameter = 19.05 mm) is sandwiched between the gritblasted ends of two specimens. As shown in Figure 3, this assembly is loaded in a copper die. The fixture is designed to create proper alignment of the bonding surfaces, to allow a load to be applied during bonding, and for fast, uniform, controlled heating and cooling of the bonded assembly. A consistency study confirmed that the joint temperature and the monitoring temperature remain close throughout the process as shown in Figure 4. Hence the die temperature is monitored and controlled.

PROCESS CYCLE

Because PEKEKK is a semi-crystalline polymer, the mechanical properties are highly dependent on the process induced morphology. It has been well established that a polymer's crystallinity is highly dependent on its processing conditions [8]. In this study, by varying the thermal history of the polymer during joint consolidation, we investigate the growth of these transcrystalline regions (TCR) on the adherend substrate and the resultant effects on adhesive joint strength.

This study investigates the influence of hold time above melt temperature (T_m), hold time at the isothermal recrystallization temperature (T_{iso}), and cooling to ambient temperature (T_a). Hold time above the melt temperature must be sufficient for the polymer to completely melt and wet the titanium surface and eliminate the residual spherulitic crystallinity in the original film material. Both hold time at the isothermal crystallization temperature and the cooling rate will affect the crystallinity of the polymer which will in turn affect the strength of the adhesive joint. The optimum isothermal crystallization temperature is defined as the temperature at which crystallization occurs at the fastest rate. At T_{iso} , the amount of time required for an amorphous specimen to achieve maximum exothermic heat flow of the DSC thermogram when held at a given temperature is at a minimum [9].

A controlled bonding cycle was defined to include the following stages:

1. heat above T_m ,
2. soak above T_m ,
3. cool to T_{iso} ,
4. soak at T_{iso} , and
5. cool to ambient temperature T_a .

DESIGN OF EXPERIMENTS

This study investigates the effects of the process parameters on adhesive strength at the following levels:

- hold time above melt temperature (5, 10, 15, and 20 minutes),
- hold time at crystallization temperature (5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 minutes), and
- cooling rate (≈ 100 °C/minute vs. ≈ 20 °C/minute).

Five samples ($n=5$) are created for each of the 40 possible combinations of time at melt, recrystallization time and cooling rate. The faster cooling rate is achieved by forced convection of water through passages in the bonding fixture. The slower cooling rate is achieved by forced convection of air.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

After bonding, the specimens are tested using an Instron Series IX Automated Materials Testing System 6.05 using a crosshead speed of 5.08 mm/minute. Average tensile strength and standard deviations are plotted in Figures 5 and 6. There are no obvious trends displayed in the two graphs. However, one can discern readily that the peak value on each graph occurs at a soak time of 20 minutes and a crystallization time of 25 minutes. In addition, the strength of the joints formed with slow cooling are consistently stronger than those formed with fast cooling. Figure 7 brings attention to the parts with a 25 minute hold time at T_{iso} . Holding at T_{iso} for 25 minutes produced the tightest standard deviation as well as the strongest parts. By holding the bond assembly above the melt temperature for 20 minutes, soaking at T_{iso} for 25 minutes, and using slow cooling to ambient temperature, joints with an average joint strength of 137 MPa with a standard deviation of 1.7 MPa were made. These values have superseded the tensile values in prior studies [4,5].

Due to the complexity of the design of experiments the results are examined statistically using a SAS program [10]. The tensile strength is a function of soak time, crystallization time and cooling rate. Statistically this is represented by the following:

$$y_{ijkl} = m + A_i + B_j + C_k + A_i B_j + A_i C_k + B_j C_k + A_i B_j C_k + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

- y tensile strength,
- m mean strength value,
- A, B, C function of independent variables (soak time, crystallization time, and cooling respectively),
- i, j, k specific test levels of the independent variables, and
- ϵ random error.

The analysis of variance indicates that soak time, crystallization time, and cooling type are significant factors affecting the tensile strength of the adhesive joint. The SAS output indicates that these individual factors are significant at the 99.99% level. Also, there are significant interactions between some of these factors. The exact nature of these interactions is not obvious. However, there are no significant interactions between soak and cooling or crystallization and cooling. Thus the equation for tensile strength reduces to the following:

$$y_{ijkl} = m + A_i + B_j + C_k + A_i B_j + A_i B_j C_k + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

A Student-Newman-Keuls (SNK) test is performed to identify trends in the data. The results indicate that tensile strength increases with soak time above the melt temperature up to a soak time of 15 minutes. This phenomenon can be seen in Figures 5 and 6, where there is a decrease in tensile strengths at a soak time of 20 minutes for most crystallization times.

A second trend identified by the SNK test is that longer cooling times, whether by extended times at the crystallization temperature or slow cooling to ambient temperature, results in higher tensile strengths. This can be seen by examination of Figures 5 and 6. Additionally, another important effect is seen by long hold times at T_{iso} . The variability in strength decreased as crystallization time increased.

As soak time increases up to the 15 minute level, the tensile strength increases. However, after this point, the adhesive joint strength actually decreases with an increase in soak time. During soak above melt temperature, residual crystallinity is eliminated gradually. The reduction of the presence of residual crystallinity that occurs with longer soak times is expected to cause an increase in the failure load of the joint. The reason for the increase in strength is because residual spherulitic crystallinity inhibits the growth of transcrystalline regions on the substrate [11].

The tensile load is expected to increase with soak time until a time is reached where all residual spherulitic crystallinity has been removed. Therefore there will be nothing to obstruct the growth of the transcrystalline layers on the adherend surfaces. In addition, the nucleation and growth of spherulitic crystallinity during cooling will be minimized. After the point when the residual crystallinity has been removed, further hold time above the melt temperature will not significantly affect the tensile strength, resulting in a leveling off of the tensile strength.

The experimental results, however, show a decrease in tensile strength at the 20 minute soak level on the order of 8% from the 15 minute soak level. By inspecting the failed surfaces the reason for this phenomenon becomes evident (see Fig. 8). In general, the samples soaked for 20 minutes show an increased number of voids and unwetted surfaces. These observations indicate excessive polymer squeeze out has occurred.

Extended time above the melt temperature while under pressure forces the polymer out of the joint. Because of the polymer squeeze-out, there is minimal polymer at the interface. As the melted polymer is cooled, shrink voids are created as the polymer contracts. Unwetted regions occur because of metal-to-metal contact of the adherend surfaces. This strength reduction mechanism also results from excessive polymer squeeze out.

An LVDT based data acquisition system was developed for on-line measurement of the film displacement of the film over time. First, two titanium mushrooms with no polymer film are placed in the fixture. These specimens undergo a typical process cycle and the displacement is recorded over time (See Fig. 9). Afterwards, the same process is repeated but with the polymer this time and the displacements are measured. By subtracting the two curves, the displacement of the film over time is generated (See Fig. 10). In this manner, the expansion and contraction of the titanium mushrooms and fixture elements are measured and compensated for when determining the film displacement. This setup can be a powerful tool for monitoring the bonding process real-time and on-line control of bond line thickness.

In addition to soak time, crystallization time and cooling rate greatly affect the adhesive joint strength. Tensile strength increases as crystallization time increases. Also tensile strength increases with slower cooling. Both high crystallization times and slow cooling rates create high levels of crystallization in the polymer which in turn increases the strength of the joint overall.

The cohesive nature of failure has been confirmed using x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. Multiple scans were taken of the fractured surface of a specimen that had processed with a hold time of 20 minutes above T_m , a hold time of 25 minutes at T_{iso} , and had been slow cooled to T_g . No titanium peak was present, indicating that the polymer covers the entire surface of the tensile specimen and that the failure is cohesive. Because the failure of the joint is primarily cohesive, two conclusions can be readily deduced: the joint strength depends on the extent of crystallization, and a high strength interfacial layer is created between the metal and polymer film.

SUMMARY

Because the failure mode is primarily cohesive, the joint strength is limited by the level of crystallization. Thus, depending on the processing conditions, the level of TCR can be maximized and the joint strength can be made to exceed that of the neat polymer. Typically, the bulk adhesive will be a mixture of crystalline regions, both transcrystalline regions growing from the substrate and spherulitic regions nucleating in the bulk polymer. In this study, the nature of the processing was shown to enhance and accentuate the growth of the transcrystalline regions while eliminating the spherulitic regions. Accordingly we conclude that the transcrystalline regions create an adhesive joint strength that surpasses the neat polymer strength.

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Figure 1. Chemical formula for Ultradek.

Figure 2. Titanium alloy tensile specimens

Figure 3. Bonding Fixture

Figure 4: Typical process thermal cycle

Figure 5: Tensile strength results for fast cooling

Figure 6: Tensile strength results for slow cooling

Figure 7: Tensile strength results for specimens with a 25 minute hold at T_{ico}

Figure 8: SEM of fractured surface, including voids

— Displacement without Film
 - - Displacement with film

Figure 9: LVDT measurement of titanium with and without film

Figure 10: Joint thickness during processing as a function of time